

Thursday, March 24, 2016 5:17:38 AM

#	Query	Limiters/Expanders	Last Run Via	Results
S4	S1 AND S2 AND S3	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - MEDLINE	88
S3	((MH "Exercise+") OR (MH "Physical Therapy Modalities") OR (MH "Exercise Movement Techniques+") OR (MH "Exercise Therapy+") OR ((MH "Postural Balance") AND (therap* OR training* OR exercise*))) OR (TX (exercise OR physical N3 therapy OR physiotherapy OR pilates OR ((muscle N3 strength) OR resistance OR balance) N3 (training OR therapy))))	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - MEDLINE	404,190
S2	TI (((motor N3 control) OR (neuromuscular N3 control) OR (motor N3 skill) OR (cognit* N3 motor) OR (cognitive N3 trunk) OR feedback OR (swiss N3 ball)) N6 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR TI ((cognit* OR propriocept* OR coordinative OR voluntary OR deliberat* OR intentional* OR willful OR wilful OR purpose* OR designed OR planned OR intended) N6 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR TI (sensorimotor OR sensormotor OR (sensory N3 motor) OR videogames OR exergames OR "dual task" OR proprioception OR (coordinat* N3 muscle*)) OR AB (((motor N3 control) OR (neuromuscular N3 control) OR (motor N3 skill) OR (cognit* N3 motor) OR (cognitive N3 trunk) OR feedback OR (swiss N3 ball)) N6 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR AB ((cognit* OR propriocept* OR coordinative OR voluntary OR deliberat* OR intentional* OR willful OR wilful OR purpose* OR designed OR planned OR intended) N6 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR AB (sensorimotor OR sensormotor OR (sensory N3 motor) OR videogames OR exergames OR "dual task" OR proprioception OR (coordinat* N3 muscle*))	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - MEDLINE	100,574
S1	((((MH "Torso+") OR TX (torso OR trunk OR back OR abdomen OR pelvis OR thorax)) AND TX (muscle N3 strength" OR ((muscle N3 composition) AND (balance OR "functional performance" OR (falls AND (association OR relationship OR correlation)))))) OR TX (trunk OR core OR postural) N3 (strenght* OR stabili*)) AND ((MH "Aged+") OR TX ((aged OR elder*) N3 (person* OR patient* OR man OR men OR woman OR women OR people)))	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - MEDLINE	1,408